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Bangrus of Arunachal Pradesh: An Ethnographic Profile

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Abstract

The present paper reports the ethnographic profile of an unknown or unrecognised small sub-tribe of Nyishi namely Bangru living in Sarli circle of Kurung Kumey district in Indian State of Arunachal Pradesh. A total of 15 villages from the circle were selected for the study. The data were collected using a set of ethnographic techniques viz., observation, informal interviews with the villages and in-depth interviews with the key informants in the community. Within this study, I attempt to provide a general ethnographic outline of traditional Bangru society and culture as it existed a years ago when it was still relatively untouched by outside influences. My objective is to offer a systemic compilation of ethnographic data on traditional Bangru society, which may be helpful to those keen to know about Bangrus and to those interested in this region as any accounts of this land and its people are still not available.

Keywords: Tribe; Sub-tribe; Ethnography; Bangru; Nyishi, Arunachal Pradesh; Kurung Kumey

1. Introduction

The Bangru is an unknown or unrecognised small sub-tribe with a population of around 2000 people inhabiting mainly the Sarli administrative circle of Kurung Kumey district (erstwhile Lower Subansiri) in northern fringe of central Arunachal Pradesh, bordering the Tibet (China). They are seen spread in Sarli town and in a few villages viz. Bala, Lee, Lower Lichila, Upper Lichila, Machane, Milli, Molo, Nade, Namju, Palo, Rerung, Sape, Sate, Wabia, and Walu.

Till date, the Bangru is considered as the sub-tribe of the larger Nyishi tribe though they are differs in their origins and dialects. However, it is evident that both have somewhat similar socio-cultural specialties due to association with each other since long back. The major clans like Pisa, Milli, Sape, Mallo, Tagang and some

minor clans existed within Bangru cluster. Among these clans, Pisa clan is somewhat more advanced than its counterparts. The origin of the Bangru is not apparent but it is certain that its origin is unparalleled with the Nyishi though they are similar in their physical appearance and are well versed in Nyishi dialect. It is believed that they were the descendants of the children who were born out of the *Ju* (Sun).

This study presents a conceptual framework on the historical development of the Bangru community of Kurung Kumey district. It is intended to provide a critical perspective. This study also describes how the Bangru maintained the elements of traditional culture in their day to day life. The study attempts to textualise the oral history of the Bangru by incorporating their perspectives of the past.

This study is centered on the Bangrus whose main dwelling place has been Sarli circle of Kurung Kumey district, who are economically and educationally backward and are also deprived of many facilities enjoyed by the people belonging to other ethnic groups. This study will also touch upon the impact of modernisation on the culture of these people and how their original culture is in danger of extinction. This study has selected all Bangru inhabited villages of Sarli circle as the area of study.

2. Objectives of the Study

While this study is an ethnographic in nature, the study has been based on the following basic objectives:

- To know who are the Bangrus, their origin, migration and oral tradition.
- To provide a basic ethnographic understanding on the society and culture of this little known frontier sub-group of Nyishi.
- To understand their livelihood strategies.

3. Methods of Study

This study is based on the data collected through various ethnographic tools and techniques. The ethnographic techniques include in-depth interviewing with key-informants in the community (such as village elders, leaders, etc.), informal and unstructured discussions and observation. Standard guidelines have been followed during the collection of the ethnographic data (Pelto and Pelto, 1978). During the selection of the informants, gender and age wise division of population has also been taken into consideration. The fieldworks were conducted in Bangru inhabited villages of Sarli Circle, an administrative circle in Kurung Kumey district of Arunachal Pradesh.

Notes have also been taken about the Bangrus with the help of the interviews with the people who know and have some knowledge on the various aspects of Bangru. Since there is dearth or nonexistence of any literature with particular reference to Bangru, available literatures on the Nyishis and official records/documents potted in district headquarter of Kurung Kumey i.e. Koloriang has been used as secondary sources of data.

4. Universe of Study

The Bangru a tribal group spread over 15 villages in Sarli circle of Kurung Kumey District of Arunachal Pradesh constitute the universe of the study. The socio-economic status of the inhabitants of these areas varies greatly due to a number of factors, e.g. transportation and communication facilities, agricultural practice, availability of resources exposure to the modern development, culture contact with other communities, etc. Since the Bangru constitutes unit of study, basic information, was collected in respect of the universe through a comprehensive household survey schedule. Further, detailed information in respect of villages were collected using multiple data gathering devices, to make an in-depth investigation of the issues concerning people's participation and development of the target group. Selection was made to all the Bangru inhabited villages because Bangru people are solely concentrated in these villages though some populace are migrate out of their villages in recent times.

5. Bangru: An Ethnographic Profile

Bangru, an assumed sub-tribe of Nyishi inhabit the Sarli Circle, an administrative circle of former Lower Subansiri District, now part of Kurung Kumey District; live in what may be called as "*Ultima Thule of Kurung Kumey District*". Since time immemorial, they have met their subsistence requirements through mixed economic activities like agriculture (Jhum and Settled), hunting, fishing, gathering and other subsistence activities. Isolated in their remote, inhospitable, and high-mountain environment, the Bangrus have had to find practical solutions to such basic problems as dearth of arable land for cultivation, lack of sufficient water for irrigation, and escalating population pressure on resources. The construction of terraces and traditional irrigation channels, a ritual complex that ensured the optimal use of seasonal conditions and limited time and space, and a system of communal and private land ownership that applied to this high-altitude region, were just some of the Bangrus' solutions to these problems.

With the formation of Kurung Kumey District on 16th April, 2001, and the opening of all-weather link road from Koloriang, a district headquarter, in the first decade of 21st century i.e. 2000s A.D., which ended region's centuries of relative isolation, the Bangrus have found themselves confronted with new and unprecedented social, economic, and political circumstances. The effects of these conditions include alterations in land-use patterns, cropping, and the erosion of ecologically sound institutions for the management of resources and the coordination of a complex set of subsistence activities.

5.1. Origin and Migration of the Bangrus

Like most of the tribes in Arunachal Pradesh, the history on the origin and migration of the Bangru is vague and documentarily absent for lack of written script culture. There is no earlier reference made to these people for documenting their histories, customs and traditions which are very unique in it. Non documentation is due to the fact that no scholar have ever paid a visit to the land of Bangrus, who inhabiting one of the most remotest and inaccessible regions of Arunachal Pradesh. What little is known about the history of their origin and migration comes from their oral tradition which are well profound among the tribals across the world.

The Bangru believe their migration to the present habitat in Sarli circle of Kurung Kumey district through a place called *Neto-Nello Puko*, a place where the people believe to be falling/bring down from *Ludlu* (Sky/Heaven) by *Aneya Ju* (Mother Sun). Unlike many tribes of Arunachal Pradesh, they traced their origin directly from the *Ju* (Sun). It is to be noted here that within Bangru there are two factions/clans i.e. general Bangru (*Phujoju* and *Milliju* and other minor groups) and *Sape* who have different route of origin and migration. According to the legend among the first group, over the course of time, Bangrus they moved to areas nowadays called Sarli from a place called *Neto-Nello Puko*. According to some of the respondents, earlier the word *Ju* which implies the Mother Sun, to whom they believe as their ancestor was suffixed with every clan name. Accordingly they were identified as '*Phujoju*' (Pisa), '*Milliju*' (Milli), '*Malloju*' (Mallo), *Tagangju* (Tagang), etc. But, with the course of time, this '*Ju*' word was gradually avoid to used by the people and in contemporary situation only the clan name remain such as Pisa, Milli, Mallo, Tagang, etc.

According to Bangru mythology, thousands of years ago the Bangru migrated somewhere from Tibet and set up their inhabitation in the place that we now call Sarli and in its adjoining areas. The Bangrus prefer to call themselves '*Taju-Bangru*' but till date all these people are known as a sub-tribe of Nyishi to the outsiders. Indeed, it is not ascertained as to when Bangrus have entered in the present inhabitants; the most popular belief is that Bangru have migrated from Tibet, although there is no historical evidence to support this belief. People believe that there is another branch of Bangru which they call them as *Wadu-Bangru*¹. Those people are believed to be moved towards the western route i.e. the present East and West Kameng districts. Through this they believed that Aka and Miji (Sajolang) tribes are their same descendants which come under *Wadu-Bangru* branch. To prove this, they gave an example by comparing their *Phujoju* and *Milliju* with Miji's (Sajolang) *Rijiju* and *Khonjuju*.

On the other hand, the second group i.e. Sape clan traced their migration route from a place called *Jiila-Ralla*. This group is considered to be a late entrant in the present habitats who were come to help the first group during warfare. These people assumed themselves as of same descendants to Memba and Khamba who were migrated towards east i.e. present Mechuka and Tuting regions of West and Upper Siang respectively. Here it is pertinent to note that the two groups have different migratory routes with different ancestral history. But after reaching and settling in the present place both the groups are speaking same language and following same customs and traditions, though with little variation.

5.2. Demographic Composition

Bangru, numbering about 1,023² (39.35%) out of approximately 2,600 persons in the Sarli circle is one of the less-known tribes of Arunachal Pradesh, presently dwelling in one administrative centre i.e. Sarli Town and in more than 15 villages of the circle in Kurung Kumey district. Although there is no separate Census record on this community, however, according to the data gathered, the Bangru account for about 1.14% of the total population of Kurung Kumey district. The present Bangru population in different villages of Sarli Circle is alphabetically presented in the following table.

¹ There is no evidence on the relations of the first group with Aka and Miji and second group with Memba and Khamba. The information is entirely in accordance with the narrations of the informants.

² This is in accordance with the recent revised electoral rolls carried out in the month of January, 2011. This is exclusively the population of persons having 18 years of age and above. No separate population statistic for Bangrus is available yet.

Table 1: Distribution of Bangru Population in Different Villages

Village	Total Population	Male	Female
Bala	10	5	5
Lee	64	36	28
Lichila (Lower)	72	32	40
Lichila (Upper)	54	29	25
Machane	65	35	30
Milli	102	45	57
Molo	22	12	10
Nade	12	5	7
Namju	33	18	15
Palo	30	11	19
Sape	152	75	77
Sarli Town	306	134	172
Sate	28	7	21
Wabia	66	24	42
Walu	6	2	4
Total	1023	471	552

Source: The Electoral Registration Office, Koloriang.

5.3. Language

Bangru language may be included in the Tani Group/Upper Assam of Tibeto-Burman language family, though no evidence is available on its language affiliation. It is different from languages of Nyishi and Puroik though they have socially and culturally close affinity among them. However, it is worth noting that the Bangru language has been largely influenced by Nyishi and very much a mixed form of speech at present. But it would not be wrong to opine that the language of Bangru is remarkably pure. Due to intermingling of Nyishi, Bangru and Puroik languages there reflects some affinities in their verbal communication.

5.4. The Settlement Pattern and Housing

The Bangru settlement is small in terms of its size and population. As per my field records, the total population of the Bangru villages varied between 6-306 persons, the highest being the population of 306 persons observed at Sarli Town, while the lowest is 6 persons in Walu village. This is because a person is living with his Nyishi relative in the village. However, a typical Bangru settlement usually consists of 50 to 100 populations. Each of these small settlements inhabited by about 10-20 households is known as *Neye* (village). It is also found that 5-10 hamlets on a particular hill are combined given a village name.

The typical Bangru settlement is characterized by sparse distribution with little disorderliness. The houses are distributed unevenly in the settlement area. Many a time, the houses are constructed wherever a place is available. Traditional households in the Bangru settlement are thatched and uniform in their structure. However, with the passage of time, such traditional thatched houses are replaced/being replaced with modern day's CGI sheets (tin sheets) to whom people deem more comfortable and secure to use. When the sons separate from their parents usually after marriage, they construct another house adjacent to their parent's house. If there is no space available, they may construct at some other place nearby.

6. Social Organisation of the Bangrus

Bangru society is patriarchal with a distinctive character of tribal endogamy and clan exogamy social system. We have already noted that the Bangru tribe is dividing into five clans and each clan few minor clans. The Bangrus' tradition is unanimous in talking of five clans although the number of sub-clan differs. The Bangrus accept the rule of the clan system and the myths, which form its background, are a key to the understanding of almost everything that is distinctive in their way of life. Violation of tribal endogamy and clan exogamy are the crimes in the Bangru society and those who break these rules are dealt with exemplary penalties. The fundamental and primary feature of social organisation is represented in every Bangru village. The presence of different clans in a village demonstrates obviously the democratic character of Bangru society.

The Bangrus constitute a well-defined and homogeneous group of people. Although their villages are scattered over a wide area, the Bangru people everywhere speak the same language and follow the same customs, have the same traditions, beliefs, rites, and ceremonies. Such small differences as they present from place to place are hardly greater than those obtaining between the villagers of adjoining regions. All are bound together by a common sentiment for the tribal name, reputation, tradition, and customs. At least five clans of Bangrus, each

bearing a distinctive name, are recognised. The word *Neye*, which appears in the names of each group, means village or settlement, and it seems probable that these five clans represent 15 original Bangru villages viz. Bala, Lee, Lichila (Lower), Lichila (Upper), Machane, Milli, Molo, Nade, Namju, Palo, Rerung, Sape, Sarli Town, Sate, Wabia and Walu which have contained the whole Bangru population.

6.1. Gyaiidya (Marriage) among the Bangrus

Marriage in Bangru society, as in all other societies is a turning point in the life history of an individual from where he branches off from the parental roof and establishes a new unit. A girl on her marriage abandons her parent's home and goes to live with her husband.

It is worth mentioning here that the Bangru, Nyishi and Puroik intermarry frequently and have some close socio-cultural relations. These intermarriages and close socio-cultural contacts have smoothed out any much difference in their marriage system, although we find finer dissimilarities among them. Marriage among the Bangrus generally involves the following considerations:

- Enhancement of social and economic status in the society.
- Addition of a working hand in the *Wua* (fields).
- Housekeeping partner.
- Meeting the biological and psychological needs.
- Procreation.
- Financial gain to the bride's in-laws.
- Increase in sphere of influence and cooperation through new relationships.

Among above considerations, the priority is given for procreation, to meet the biological and psychological needs, to need helping hand in the domestic works and for housekeeping.

Marriage in Bangru society is traditionally arranged by the parents preferably with the people of equal social status. The Bangru do not prefer marriages between specific kinsmen, for in olden days the alliance of the two families called for mutual support in fends and raids (Haimendorf, 1982:64)³. Matrimonial alliances were a means to gather allies to defend itself against attack from enemies. Marriages are also arranged to obtain some valuables of fine quality and repute which the girl's family may be having.

6.2. Lameii (Family)

Lameii (Family) in the Bangru society is the outcome of marriage. The family is a universal institution and has existed throughout the history of human society. It is the smallest social unit consisting of parents and their unmarried children. Such is a nuclear type of family which is most commonly found among the Bangrus. The family is the simplest and the most important primary group in society. It is the most basic of all social groupings. It is also the first and the most immediate social environment to which a child is exposed and it is in the family that the child develops its basic attitudes.

But with the passage of time, family has undergone changes gaining and losing valour shapes and characteristics. The present age of economic development and cultural revival have posed some new challenges to the institution of family; leading to radical changes in the structures and functions of family. However, the institution of family is surviving and will survive for the survival of the society itself.

6.3. The Clan

The basic feature of social organisation is depends on the division of the community. In Bangru also there are two distinct groups; they are *General Bangru* and *Sape*. These two groups are endogamous divisions of Bangru. Within *General Bangru* also exogamous practice is prevailing. This means a man with a particular clan identity marries a woman with a different clan membership though both of them belong to same group. For instance, a member of *Pisa* clan could marry a member belong to *Milli* clan though both the clans has identical affiliation within *General Bangru* group. Each clan holds a village or group of villages and have the names from the name of place where they presently inhabit. The *General Bangru* group is divided into four major clans with some minor clans and *Sape* group is considered to be existed with only one clan with same name of the group. The *General Bangru* group is consisted of clans like *Pisa*, *Milli*, *Mallo or Mullo or Mullong*, *Tagang*, and few minor clans.

6.4. The Village

Anthropologists have, from the very beginning, studied the village as an autonomous human institution from the point of view of political institutions and processes, social interactions, inter-personal and inter-family

³ This was refers to the Nyishi society to whom Bangru society have basic similarities in their marriage customs.

relationships, etc., and have come to the conclusion that the village, despite various influences and changes, has retained its particular traditional institution. The Bangru village, being the most traditional and ancient institution, crystallised a whole system of social, political, and ritual structures.

While the clan is the most important social unit in Bangru society, the traditional polity is based upon the village. The village is a territorial unit claiming an exclusive right to a tract of land with clear boundaries. On occasions the village drew from its members a strong spirit of cohesion, and there is considerable local patriotism based upon a host of legends and colourful history of the village's past exploits. Another important aspect of the village is its function as a unit of defence. Most villages (or its member clans) are sometime in state of feud, and there is a need for perpetual alertness and vigilance, as well as for strong defences that would enable the villagers to resist attack without inordinate difficulty or great loss of life. For this reason many villages are built on the summits of hills, while a convenient source of water enhanced the selection of the site. The villages are permanent and they are encased in extensive and impressive circumvallation, which represented the efforts and innovations of many generations.

6.5. Bangru Guii-Koro (Kinship)

Kinship system is usually seen as a method of organising marriage relations between groups. Through marriage, members are recruited to kinship groups. The kinship is helpful to study the means of genealogies. The Bangrus are having a well planned kinship and which has got some interesting features also. The most important feature is the use of the same term *Alo* for grandfather on one hand but on the other for father-in-law (of both man and woman). Another feature may be found in the using of term *Ako* and *Mesebya* for all brothers and sisters (elder or younger) respectively. *Mesebya* is also used to refer to father's sister. The important features of the Bangru kinship are the system of existence of two well-marked groups of terms expressing bonds of kinship. Similarly, with regard to grandfather and grandmother they call *Alo* and *Asse* respectively and it is used to refer to both paternal and maternal grandfather and grandmother. *Asse* is also simultaneously used for both grandmother and mother-in-law or wife's mother.

Another interesting pointing is that the Bangru system has two set of kinship terms, those used in direct address and those used when speaking of relatives who do not correspond closely with one another. This system distinguishes widely between elder and younger member of the family and clan. The Bangrus never mention their *kiini* (mother's brother) and *alo* (wife's father). Similarly, a man is also prohibited in mentioning the name of the father-in-law and mother-in-law (*asse*). The Bangru terms of address and their equivalent words in Nyishi and English are given in the table 2. I have included the Nyishi here only to find out the similarities and dissimilarities of wordings within them.

Table 2: The Bangru Terms of Address and their Equivalent Words in Nyishi and English

Bangru Terms of Address	English Equivalent Words	Nyishi Terms of Address
Achowa	Mother's Sisters (common)	Amu/Mu
Aneya	Mother	Ane
Ako	Brother (common)	Achi/Abang/Buru
Alo	Father-in-law	Atu
Asse	Mother-in-law	Ayu
Juchobii	Sister's Son and Father's Sister's Son	Ku
Juchobya	Sister's Daughter and Father's Sister's Daughter	Ku
Kiini	Mother's Brother	Akh/Kiigh
Mechemya-Nyib	Grandson	Ku-Nyaga Huiish
Mechemya-Nyiwai	Granddaughter	Ku-Nyeme Huiish
Melgya	Husband	Nyulu
Mesebya	Sister (common)	Anyi/Barme
Mii	Wife	Nyahang
Miibi	Father	Abu
Miibo/ Miwo/Mibow	Daughter's Husband and Son-in-law	Magbu/Magtey
Minyii	Son's Wife and Daughter-in-law	Nyaahang
Muju-Nyib	Son	Ku-Nyaga
Muju-Nyiwai	Daughter	Ku-Nyeme

Source: Fieldwork (July 2011)/Bangru Villages.

7. Political Organisation of the Bangrus

Whether it is a *state* or *stateless* society (Fortes and Evans-Pritchard, 1940) or a *minimal* or *diffused* government (Mair, 1965), there exists some form of political organisation in every society. This organisation carries out the

functions of social control in the society at large. It is not necessary to differentiate between the social and political control and identifies politics as the function of society. But who controls whom, who is a leader, who are his followers, and how a leader assumes a position of control over others are crucial in the understanding of any political system, whether it is traditional or modern. In the study of a political system of a group or society, the first thing that singles itself out is *authority or leadership*.

The political organisation of the Bangru is run on democratic lines unlike some tribes of Arunachal Pradesh where autocratic chief is the sole authority of the community. The important affairs are decided by village councils consisting of elders or heads of families. The pattern of social organisation of Bangrus is not much different from the neighbouring Nyishis and Puroiks. They are dividing into five clans which are further divided into several families. The clan-wise division of the Bangrus is as follows: *Pisa, Milli, Sape, Mallo* and *Tagang*. All clans mentioned marry with each other. But they do not marry within themselves, i.e. they practice clan exogamy (Discussion with Bangru community leaders/elders, January' 2011).

In parallel with the other tribes of Arunachal Pradesh, Bangru also have certain legal system of their own i.e. customary law. Bangru customary law in its traditional manifestations is not embodied in any formal codes. There are no written laws; and although many rules of conduct are epitomised in proverbs and kindred sayings, there is also no well-defined corpus of legal maxims and principles. The laws of the Bangru are to a considerable extent inherent in the social system of the people. They exist as rights and duties developed through the course of time out of man's efforts to adjust his behaviour in relation to his fellows and to the physical environment he shares and exploits with them; and have become accepted from their very nature, from the fact that they satisfy the more fundamental and common needs of life in society, as binding and obligatory.

7.1. Traditional Bangru Political System: Now

In contrast to the earliest norms of justice dispensation through in the Bangru society, the roles of village council including the role of Gaon Burahs (GBs) are diminishing. The factors behind such changes are clear. The introduction of modern electoral political system in the form of Panchayat Raj System and the abrupt coming of Christianity are responsible for the diminishing role of village council. People nowadays approach directly to village panchayat as the panchayat has also right of framing rules and regulations for the welfare of the villagers. On the other hand, those who are converted to Christianity have no more belief in the customary law; due to which they didn't approach the village council for settling any dispute.

However, there is no instance of influencing the functioning of the village council by any political parties. They are not able to influence the functioning, as the political parties are mostly seasonal. Government is taken steps to stimulate the village council by announcing allowances and honorarium for Gaon Burahs (GBs). This seems to be a kind of reorganisation of the village council. On Independence Day, the District administrator recognises the Gaon Burahs (GBs) by awarding red-coat and other honorarium.

8. Livelihood Strategies of Bangru

The Bangru people mostly resided in close proximity to forest and fringe of the river in the past. This is so due to their dependency on products for firewood, close access to wild medicinal plants used to cure disease and fishery as their main source of income for livelihoods. They started practicing shifting cultivation. They have generated enormous knowledge on a large number of plants species on which they have depended for centuries. Due to this, forests were most important resources for them in terms of food, fibre, medicine, housing materials, fodder and various other needs.

As information from Bangrus⁴, people lived in the group near the forest and fringe of the river because their life is depended on the forests and rivers. They practiced shifting cultivation, hunting wild animals and gathering wild fruits and herbs. The Bangrus are expert in capturing wild animals, perfected in hunting and fishing. They used various traps and tools and natural poisons while fishing in rivers and streams.

Agriculture is of the utmost importance to the Bangru economy. The Bangrus depend upon their plots not only for the major part of their sustenance but also for a cash income since few years back. The staple crop cultivated by the Bangru is *ey/eaii* (paddy); but there are other crops like maize, *tamai* (millet), finger-millet which supplement the rice at regular interval. Other than all these crops, there is one such tree called *Lavo*⁵ known as famine food which supplement their foods at very difficult time like during famine like situation very often due to bamboo flowering. This tree is particularly predominant among the neighbouring Puroiks, for whom, it is serving as staple food.

⁴ Based on the interviews held during the fieldwork period (January, 2011).

⁵ This was the staple food of the Bangrus before they shift for contemporary modes of cultivation. The term is called as *Tasse* and *Rangbang* among Nyishis and Puroiks respectively.

Briefly, the Bangru farming practices are as follows: a plot is planted with paddy, maize, and other eatables for one year. In some of the villages, plot is allowed to lie fallow for years. After the years of fallowing, it is again put back into cultivation. In other words, plots carry crops on alternate years. The fallow periods of the plots ranges from 4-5 years. In theory, the cycle of fallow and carrying crops continues indefinitely but the Bangru people perceived that some plots “tire” more quickly than others and these, after a few years, must be allowed a longer period of rest than the usual one year.

9. Religious Beliefs and Ritual Practice

Belief system and ritual practices plays an extremely important part in the religious life of the Bangru. There is a well-defined belief in certain supernatural beings able to influence for good or for evil the destinies of the living. Their religious beliefs and practices have a basic similarity with those of their neighbouring tribes like Nyishi and Puroik. Like other tribes, they have also developed myths about the creation, the Sun and the Moon, the origin of man and about death. Their concept of the soul, which they call *arey*, is that a separation of the soul and the body takes place at the time of death.

The traditional Bangru religion is *Donyi-Polo* or *Donyi-Poloism*⁶. They believe that some trees, stones and hills are the abodes of the spirits. Like all animistic religions, that of the Bangrus consists of the belief in a multitude of beneficent and malevolent spirits, to some is attributed the creation of the world, to the others the control of natural phenomena, and the destinies of man from birth to death are governed by a host of divinities whose anger must be appeased by sacrifice through a ritual ceremonies.

9.1. The Bangru Religious Beliefs

The whole belief systems of Bangru religion may be categorised as follows:

- Belief in Supernatural Powers.
- Belief in the Supreme God.
- Belief in Spirits World.
- Belief in Magic and Witchcraft.
- Belief in Worship, Prayer and Sacrifice.
- Belief in Life after Death.
- Belief in Soul.
- Belief in *Tyameii* (Dream).

9.2. The Bangru Religious Practices

The Bangru religious practices are inherent in their day-to-day ritual performances which can be categorised into following:

- Ritual to Vindicate the Truth.
- Ritual Related to Agriculture.
- Ritual Related to Evil Practices.
- Ritual on Human Death.
- Ritual for Immediate Healing.
- Ritual Related to Creation.
- Ritual Related to Purification and Divine Favour.

10. Festival System

Like many tribal societies, the Bangru also have their festival system. The complexity of the many clans and their interlocking nature are crucial aspects of the festival system, and notable when found at the Bangrus' technological level of development. The major agricultural festival of the Bangrus is similar to Nyishis of Koloriang area where they celebrated *Longte-Yullo* or simply *Longte* or *Lungte* as major festival. More interesting fact is that the myth behind the festival is entirely of Nyishis; and Bangrus have no independent myth on the origin of this festival though they are entirely a different ancestral group.

Literally, *Longte* means a large wooden barricade/fence which is erected on community basis in the belief that this demarcates the domain of humans and spirits from ill-intended trespass. This festival is celebrated on the advent of spring season in the month of April (*Lachar-Polu*). The festivals, an aspect of Bangru religion in the broadest sense, are ceremonies that instill, especially in the young, profound feelings for and beliefs in the Bangru way of life. The festivals provide guidelines for acting out traditional roles, thereby sanctioning them, as

⁶ These terms in Bangru language are known as *Ju* for Sun and *Libaying* for Moon respectively. Since Bangru does not have a religion with their terms; so the *Donyi* and *Polo* is being used.

well as social settings in which the individual can experience joy and express love. The festivals contribute in this way to the high social cohesion that is characteristic of the Bangru socio-cultural system.

11. Christianity among the Bangrus

The study of the Bangrus' traditions and institutions would be incomplete without taking into account the influence of Christian missionaries. Christianity has a significant influence upon the Bangrus and apart from missionary activities, they undertake many welfare activities towards the people. Actually, Bangrus conversion to Christianity started in the late part of last century and during the earlier part of present century when Baptists Christian Missionaries under the aegis of Kurung Kumey Baptist Mission Field (KKBMF) had set their foot at the Bangru inhabited regions and then some other missionaries started to work. With the influence of Christianity, they shifted from their old beliefs on *Ju-Libaying* (Donyi-Poloism) but they attend mostly their basic traditions and social customs.

The recent exposure to western and Christian ideas, especially education and religious practices, has resulted to a change in the Bangru way of life. This change caused a division into traditionalists and non-traditionalists. The traditionalists are being those regard themselves as the custodian of tribal customs, and the non-Traditionalist being those who have changed their traditional way of life to adopting Christianisation/Westernisation. It is however important to note that these group are not geographically distinct, but they live side by side in their communities and share many aspect of their social life. It is important to note that there are also these who have been Westernised/Christianised but they are still interested in maintaining a typical traditional Bangru way of life.

12. Conclusion

Every tribal group or society has its own unique characteristics, value-systems, traditional mores, life-attitudes, social hierarchies, religion and traditions. It has its own approach to life and death, disease and sickness, individual and community, and above all, a sense of identity. This sense of identity or cultural self-image always has positive and negative facets; it defines the traits of solidarity and uniqueness of the tribal group, and also seeks differences with other groups in the larger society around.

The study of this closely knit tribal group termed '*The Bangrus*' is of importance from the point of sociological and anthropological insight into their social system and other overt aspects of their society cannot be denied for the simple reason that no study had ever previously been undertaken. The Bangru society needs to be more profoundly studied and analysed from other socially scientific aspects.

As this is the first study on Bangrus, difficulties in drawing conclusions from the empirical evidence collected through various ethnographic methods and techniques naturally presented themselves; but, I had also simultaneously taken great care in recording the data of my participant and non-participant observations, it may venture to claim that the data are fairly accurate and may be relied upon as adequate insights into the workings of the Bangru societal constitution.

This ethnographic piece of writing on Bangrus is a humble attempt to highlight the earlier history and culture of the people which is not available as yet. In this study I have focused on traditional Bangru society and culture as it existed long before. Today much has changed, and much is changing, for the Bangrus who find themselves confronted with new social, political, and economic circumstances.

13. Suggestions

The followings are the some of the suggestions which I have made on the basis of the study made on the *Bangrus of Arunachal Pradesh*.

13.1 Need for Employment Opportunities

Some of the traditional occupations of Bangrus are basket making, fishing, hunting, trees cutting, etc. These works have no much demand in these days as industries and modern equipments have replaced them. At this juncture the Government has to take necessary steps to provide employment opportunities for them. Some of the items which they produce have no market; there are also middle man's exploitations. In this regard government and other Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) have to make schemes and plans to find proper marketing, even to export some of their arts and handicraft items. This will surely help them to come out of their poverty and economical backwardness. Government must create some employment opportunity for them according to their traditionally inherited skills and talents.

13.2 Need for Improvement of Transport and Communication Facility

As many of their villages are situated in remote places where they lack proper infrastructures and transport facilities. They have to depend on the nearby small towns like Sarli and Koloriang for anything and everything. Most of the places transportation and communication is an issue. They have to go to the nearby town for medical, educational and any governmental assistance purpose. Lack of transport infrastructures and communication facilities also limit their knowledge of rights and benefits. In this way most of them are not aware and able to enjoy the rights and benefits. This causes them to deny the chances for good job, education and medical care. So it is an essential need that government and other Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) look in to this matter to help and improve the road transport and communication facilities of their villages.

13.3 Need for Improvement of Basic Amenities

Bangrus generally do not worry about any such global issues or political issues, but they are only concerned about their survival issues such as housing, food and clothing. They live in far-flung remote villages where they lack all basic amenities. Though Government provides many schemes for their basic needs unfortunately these are not becoming 100% reality for them. In this regard Government and NGOs should entrust on trustworthy organisation in giving contract work for their development.

13.4 Need for More Emphasis on Education

Most of the Bangrus are living in various kinds of depravities (social, economical and political). Education is the only key solution which helps them to overcome all of these depravities. Education needs to be highly emphasised among the Bangrus. Most of the schools in the villages are in myriad of problems like lack of infrastructures, textbooks, etc. Many of the Bangru children dropouts from the school only reason of distance to the school and economic backwardness.

When look at the population and educational challenges of Bangrus, the openings and opportunities are very limited. So it is the need of the hour that both Government and NGOs should give strong emphasis on the educational development of the Bangrus since education is the root cause of all developments.

13.5 Need for Improvement of the Health Facilities

Most of the Bangrus are living in the below the poverty line, for this reason they are not getting the rich protein food items. They also live in an unhygienic atmosphere in the settlements as a result many of them suffer from various kinds of diseases and anaemic problems. Though there are several organisations working among them still there is no satisfactory development in their health related problems. There are many in the villages addicted to bad habits such as alcoholism, smoking and chewing tobacco. This causes several diseases among them. There is a great need for good health service and awareness programmes among them. This can surely bring about a great transformation among them. There is only one primary health centre in their localities situated at Nade (New Sarli), that too without sufficient medical staffs, medicines and medical facilities. It is a need of the hour to establish more health centres near to their dwelling place. It is also important to select, train and send health workers to their area where they can make remarkable contribution to the people.

13.6 Need for Encouragement of Ethnomedicines, Arts and Handicraft items

Traditionally, they have valuable medicinal, arts and handicraft knowledge, which is being vanished away since there is no appreciation from the governmental authority. Some of their products need to find proper marketing and its values need to be propagated among the people. Traditional medicinal knowledge of Bangrus is very valuable. These medicines need to be popularised and commercialised. So that there can be economical development.

13.7 Need for Empowerment of Women

In contemporary Bangru society, women are treated as subordinate to men. Mostly women are the sufferers among the Bangru community. They have the family burdens on their shoulders such as feeding the children, going for work in the *wua* (field) and gathering food items. Giving more emphasis on women education, providing more employment opportunities, giving job oriented training, giving equal property rights along with men to women need to be considered. These may empower the status of the women in their society.

14. Some of the Key Concerns for the Bangrus

The following are some of the prime concerns of the researcher regarding the overall progress of Bangrus:

- Improve the standard of living
- Improve the socio-economic status through various developmental and income-generating activities
- Improve the employment opportunities for educated youth of poor families

- Improve the educational status
- Improve the living conditions
- Increasing the school enrolment rate
- Reducing drop out percentage
- Improving the health and nutritional status, Strengthening the basic amenities and infrastructural facilities in their habitations
- Creating awareness on the schemes and their benefits

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